

Studies of the Metal Complexes Derived from 4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one (Schiff base)

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The Schiff base, 4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one forms solid complexes with Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Cd(II) and UO₂(II). The elemental analysis, molecular weight, magnetic moment values and electronic spectral data have been used to establish the stoichiometry and structures of these compounds. Based on these studies it is concluded that Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), and UO₂(II) complexes possess octahedral structures. Cu(II), Zn(II) and Cd(II) complexes display tetrahedral structures whereas Pd(II) complex exhibits a square planar configuration.

A survey of the literature shows that no systematic studies have been carried out using ethanolamine Schiff base with acetylacetone. The present paper describes the results of the investigation on the complexes of Fe (II), Co (II), Ni (II), Cu (II), Zn (II), Pd (II), Cd (II) and UO₂(II) with 4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one (abbr, HEA).

Experimental

Materials :

Iron, cobalt, nickel, copper, zinc, palladium, cadmium and uranyl salts were of analytical reagent grade (B.D.H.). Ethanolamine and acetylacetone (LR) supplied by B. D. H. were used without further purification.

Apparatus :

Gallenkamp Semimicro ebulliometer was employed for molecular weight determinations using dioxane as the solvent for which the ebulliometric constant was found to be 214500. The combustion analysis was conducted by Hosli's electrical micro combustion furnace. Gouy apparatus was used for magnetic susceptibility measurements. The electronic absorption spectra measurements were made on Uvispeck Hilger spectrophotometer.

Preparation of the Schiff base and its metal complexes :

The Schiff base, 4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one was prepared¹ pure by refluxing a mixture of

acetylacetone (2.0 g.) and ethanolamine (1.2 g.) on a water bath for half an hour in an apparatus provided with water separator. After the reflux the contents of the flask were cooled when brownish yellow coloured solid mass separated out. It was recrystallised from methanol and preserved in a vacuum desiccator. Found : C, 58.52 ; H, 8.94 ; N, 9.67%. Calcd. for (C₇H₁₃NO₂) : C, 58.75 ; H, 9.10 and N, 9.79%. Its metal complexes were obtained by the method of Yamada *et al*^{2,3}. The pyridine solvates of Fe (II) and Ni (II) complexes were prepared⁴ by treating these complexes with distilled pyridine and warming the solutions on a steam-bath. The solutions were concentrated and kept in a vacuum desiccator for crystallization. The crystals were washed with a little absolute ethanol, then with ether and finally preserved in a vacuum desiccator. The pyridine solvates of the remaining metal complexes could not be isolated in the solid state.

Results and Discussion

On the basis of the molecular weight, elemental analysis (Table 1) and magnetic moment data (Table 2), the composition of these complexes is given by [ML₂], where LH = [CH₃C(OH)CHCH₂C=N(CH₂)₂OH] and M = Fe (II), Co (II), Ni (II), Cu (II), Zn (II), Pd (II), Cd (II) or UO₂(II).

The magnetic data of Fe (II) and Ni (II) complexes and their pyridine solvates (Table 2)

TABLE I. EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED RESULTS OF MOLECULAR WEIGHT AND ELEMENTAL ANALYSES

Name and formula of the compound	Molecular weight		Metal		Elemental Analysis Carbon		Hydrogen		Nitrogen	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} iron (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Fe (II)]	324	339.8	16.36	16.42	49.25	49.44	6.92	7.06	8.11	8.24
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} cobalt (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Co(II)]	327	342.9	17.02	17.18	49.17	49.00	7.15	7.00	8.02	8.17
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} nickel (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Ni(II)]	326	342.7	17.03	17.13	48.92	49.03	6.87	7.00	8.10	8.17
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} copper (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Cu(II)]	360	347.5	18.15	18.28	48.17	48.35	6.97	6.91	7.96	8.06
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} zinc (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Zn(II)]	335	349.4	18.60	18.72	48.15	48.08	6.72	6.87	7.93	8.02
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} palladium (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Pd(II)]	374	390.4	27.12	27.26	42.93	43.03	6.01	6.15	7.04	7.17
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} cadmium (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Cd (II)]	387	396.4	28.19	28.35	42.22	42.38	5.50	6.05	6.92	7.07
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one} uranyl (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ UO ₂ (II)]	538	554	42.87	42.96	30.18	30.33	4.21	4.33	4.95	5.06
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one pyridine} iron (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH(C ₅ H ₅ N)] ₂ Fe(II)]	483	498	11.05	11.20	57.69	57.84	6.78	6.83	11.12	11.25
Bis {4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one pyridine} nickel (II) [[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH(C ₅ H ₅ N)] ₂ Ni(II)]	487	501.1	11.63	11.75	57.25	57.48	6.67	6.79	10.97	11.18

TABLE 2. MAGNETIC MOMENTS VALUES AT 298°K.

Compound	Mass Susceptibility $\chi_m \times 10^6$	Molar Susceptibility $\chi_m \times 10^6$	Magnetic moments, μ_{eff} in B. M.
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Fe(II)]	34.02	11726.60	5.31
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Co(II)]	25.77	9003.80	4.65
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Ni(II)]	10.14	3642.82	2.96
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Cu(II)]	3.72	1459.05	1.87
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH(C ₅ H ₅ N)] ₂ Fe(II)]	24.19	12212.50	5.42
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH(C ₅ H ₅ N)] ₂ Ni(II)]	7.71	4029.27	3.11
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Zn(II)]	—	—	diamagnetic
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Pd(II)]	—	—	"
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ Cd(II)]	—	—	"
[[CH ₃ C(O)CHCH ₂ C=N(CH ₂) ₂ OH] ₂ UO ₂ (II)]	—	—	"

correspond to the presence of 4 and 2 unpaired electrons respectively in these compounds. It is also evident from these data that 4-(2-hydroxy ethylimino) pentane-2-one appears to behave as a tridentate in the Fe (II) and Ni (II) complexes. The molecular weights, 324 and 326 to Fe (II) and Ni (II) complexes respectively, thus exclude the possibility of intermolecular association and is most likely that the intramolecular bond M-OH may be present in these compounds in which M denotes Fe (II) or Ni (II). This situation may be best represented by an octahedral structure (I) for Fe (II) and Ni (II)

WHERE M = Fe (II), Ni (II) OR Co(II)

I

complexes. In the case of pyridine solvates of Fe (II) and Ni (II) complexes, it appears that two

pyridine molecules occupy the two coordination positions of the metal ion previously occupied by two -OH groups of the Schiff base. Hence an octahedral structure (II) is proposed for these

WHERE $M = Fe(II)$ OR $Ni(II)$
II

solvates. The electronic absorption spectra of Ni (II) complex in dioxane consist of an absorption band at 17200 cm^{-1} and a nearly similar band for this complex was observed in pyridine. It indicates the presence of octahedrally coordinated Ni (II) in both the solvents. The band at 17200 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the transition, ${}^3T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ of the Ni(II).

The IR data of the Co (II) complexes indicated the presence of band around 3360 cm^{-1} due to co-ordinated OH group. The electronic absorption spectra of Co (II) complex in dioxane and pyridine consist of two absorption bands with their peaks at 13600 cm^{-1} and 27030 cm^{-1} and are assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ respectively. These transitions supported by magnetic and IR data suggest the Co (II) complex to be octahedral and in this case also the Schiff base acts as a tridentate ligand.

However, the IR spectra of Cu (II) complex gave a band at 3620 cm^{-1} which indicates the presence of non bonded -OH group in it and thus the ligand functions as a bidentate. The spectra of Cu (II) complex in dioxane consist of two absorption bands with peaks at 24200 cm^{-1} and 14800 cm^{-1} . In pyridine solution of the complex nearly similar bands were observed. The band at 24200 cm^{-1} exhibits

two shoulders towards shorter wavelength and is stronger than the other band. The band at 14800 cm^{-1} and 24200 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the transition $2E \rightarrow 2T_2$ of the Cu (II), and intra ligand charge transfer respectively⁵⁻⁶.

Zn (II), Pd (II), Cd (II) and UO_2 (II) complexes were experimentally found to be diamagnetic, as expected. The pyridine solvates of these complexes could not be isolated in the solid state. All these complexes display 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry (Table 1). Based on these experimental data, Zn (II) and Cd (II) complexes possess tetrahedral structures while Pd (II) compound should display a square planar configuration. The UO_2 (II) complex under investigation most probably possess an octahedral structure⁷. These diamagnetic complexes may be represented by a general structure (III).

WHERE $M = Cd(II)$, $Zn(II)$, $Pd(II)$,
 $Cd(II)$ OR $UO_2(II)$

III

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